

Scoping Assessment of Hydrothermal Carbonization for Resource Recovery from Waste-Activated Sludge

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Abstract

Wastewater treatment plants are transitioning into water resource recovery facilities as an important step towards energy and climate neutrality. Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is a promising sludge treatment option to balance contaminant removal with resource recovery. This study investigated HTC of waste activated sludge under different conditions followed by biochemical methane potential tests. The results showed that aqueous hydrothermal liquor (AHL) produced higher methane yields than untreated waste-activated sludge (WAS), but due to organic material loss to hydrochar, total biogas production decreased. However, HTC allows the plant to process more sludge while hydrochar can serve as an additional by-product for resource recovery. Further research is needed to optimize trade-offs in energy and nutrient recovery, contaminant removal and emission mitigation.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Biogas, Hydrochar, Hydrothermal carbonization, Resource recovery, Waste activated sludge, Wastewater treatment

INTRODUCTION

Modern wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) face conflicting pressures to reduce contaminant discharge and meet higher standards for recovering nutrients (N, P) and energy while maintaining stringent emissions-reduction targets (Derco et al, 2024). Underscoring these pressures is a broader conceptual shift from WWTPs to water resource recovery facilities (WRRFs), driven by the need to valorize biomass flows and reduce society's reliance on fossil carbon (Faragò et al, 2021). Central to this transition is the management of sewage sludge (SS), which is typically generated in two stages. Primary sludge (PS) is generated first by settlement after flocculation of suspended material. Waste-Activated Sludge (WAS) is then generated by the settlement of microbial biomass following biological (secondary) treatment. These two sludge fractions are typically mixed and undergo anaerobic digestion (AD) for biogas production; however, this sequential production leads to distinct compositional profiles and differences in resource recovery and contaminant remediation potential.

Recent research has proposed the use of HTC as a promising pathway for sludge treatment. By processing sludge under autogenous subcritical water conditions (160–260°C), HTC converts organic matter into energy-dense solid (hydrochar) and an aqueous liquid fraction (AHL). Many HTC studies focus on mixed sludge or digestate, leaving the potential of HTC specifically for WAS streams underexplored (Ogunleye et al, 2024). Retrofitting WWTP with HTC for WAS may increase nutrient availability and align with the development of a sustainable bioeconomy by valorizing waste biomass but may also reduce biogas production. In complex systems facing multidimensional sustainability pressures, quantifying the degrees of potential benefits and risks can help to navigate barriers and seize opportunities to sustainable transitions. This study aims to assess the impact of a prospective retrofit of WWTP with HTC of WAS on sustainability and resource recovery potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To evaluate the relative resource recovery potential of applying HTC to WAS during sludge treatment, a reference case was constructed by acquiring data on PS and WAS composition and biogas production from Kungsängen WWTP in Västerås, Sweden (Figure 1a). A series of HTC and biological methane potential (BMP) experiments were conducted under three conditions to evaluate alternative treatment scenarios between sludge thickening and AD (Figure 1b): ALT1, at 180°C for 30 minutes, ALT2, at 210°C for 60 minutes, and ALT3, at 260°C for 120 minutes. Experimental results were scaled based on assumed 5% TS for WAS and PS after thickening.

Figure 1. System diagram of the *reference* system (a) and the *alternatives* including HTC (b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proportional compositions from WWTP data and experimental results on partitioning of nutrients and heavy metals between sludge fractions and HTC products are depicted in Table 1. Proportions are relative to the higher mass fraction, therefore any values over the mass ratio represent increased concentration in the lower mass fraction.

Table 1. Proportional distribution of SS composition between WAS and PS and between solid (HC) and liquid (AHL) fractions of HTC of WAS.

	Mass	Nutrients			Heavy metals							
		C	N	P	Zn	Cu	Cr	Ni	Pb	Cd	Hg	
WAS:PS	0.57	-	-	0.71	0.36	0.65	0.39	0.52	0.42	0.64	0.27	
ALT1	0.15	0.63	0.21	8.92	89.48	805.09	34.58	3.43	735.9	153.97	322.04	
HC:AHL	ALT2	0.11	0.59	0.14	11.71	69.06	822.66	16.43	3.91	299.81	149.37	76.82
ALT3	0.11	0.59	0.18	5.15	86.62	354.36	38.59	37.8	23.62	3.62	37.56	

Properties of Waste Activated Sludge

WAS contains a higher proportion of protein and lower carbohydrates and lipids compared to PS. This is a result of most oils, fats and organic wastes fractionating into PS (Ahnert et al, 2021). As a result, WAS contains comparatively high nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations. Heavy metals are partitioned disproportionately into PS except for copper and cadmium, which show slight densification into WAS.

Effect of Hydrothermal Carbonization

Across all three HTC conditions, most of the mass, carbon and nitrogen remains in the AHL in the form of suspended solids while metals and phosphorus remain with the hydrochar. ALT1 produced the most enriched hydrochar, with higher average concentrations of carbon, nitrogen and metals. ALT2 demonstrated the widest partitioning of nitrogen and phosphorus between hydrochar and AHL. A trend in metal solubilizing into the AHL was noticeable with increasing reaction severity. Biomethane production (BMP) tests show higher specific methane production in AHL and lower yields in hydrochar compared to raw WAS. This effect shows minor variation between ALT1 and ALT2 but shifts considerably in ALT3, introducing an approx. 3-week lag in methane production of AHL and a strong resistance to methanation in hydrochar (Figure 2). During HTC, protein-bound nitrogen is solubilized into the AHL as ammonia, which can inhibit methanogenesis (Wilson and Novak, 2009). However, in ALT3, nitrogen retention in hydrochar increases, possibly due to secondary char formation, reducing ammonia solubilization in AHL. In a continuous system with recirculation of digestate reject water, HTC would induce an ammonia enrichment that may inhibit biogas production if unaddressed, though would also offer an opportunity for improved nitrogen recovery via stripping.

System Impacts

The treatment of WAS with HTC and diversion of the solid product from AD impacts the WTPP biogas production, AD capacity, biosolids production and resource recovery potential. From a capacity perspective, the removal of hydrochar from AD frees up capacity, enabling the system to process 3-5% greater sludge loading volumes. Despite increased specific BMP in AHL, the loss of organic solids to hydrochar reduces biogas production from WAS by 30% in ALT1, 44% in ALT2 and 84% in ALT3. These values are based on a 20-day retention time, while AHL from ALT3 demonstrated the highest BMP production if retention time could be increased or the observed lag time mitigated during implementation of the HTC retrofit. In addition, there is early evidence that co-digestion with AHL may increase PS biogas yields (Villamil et al, 2020). Nonetheless, the observed correlation between reaction severity and bioavailability leads to a trade-off between BMP and hydrochar stability from a systems perspective. Emissions during storage and application of sludge biosolids remain a major obstacle to WTPP decarbonization (Yoshida et al, 2018). Reducing or reversing this effect through deposition of recalcitrant soil organic carbon may be worth reduced biogas production if the relationship can be further understood. Beyond its impact on biogas production, HTC brings in hydrochar as an additional product with potential for resource valorization. Hydrochar is sterile and phosphorus enriched, requiring less stabilization than dewatered digestate, lowering treatment costs and fuel use. It can be used for energy recovery or as a soil amendment, contributing to a circular economy. While heavy metals remain in WAS and densify in hydrochar, studies suggest that HTC lowers the bioavailability of these metals, lowering their ecotoxicity (Nahar et al, 2024). For ALT3, the resistance to methanation suggests a high proportion of recalcitrant organic matter in the hydrochar, which would contribute to long term soil carbon storage in applied as a biofertilizer.

Figure 2. The cumulative specific methane production from hydrochar and AHL relative to WAS. ALT1 (blue) and ALT2 (green) show similar behavior compared to ALT3 (red).

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Integrating HTC into WWTPs increases sludge processing capacity while introducing trade-offs between biogas production and hydrochar production. Although total biogas production is reduced due to organic matter retention in hydrochar, AHL yields more methane than WAS. Nutrient recovery improves through the separation and hydrolysis of proteaginous nitrogen, enabling direct recovery of carbon and phosphorus in hydrochar or post energy recovery for contaminated flows. Further research is necessary to parse the relationship between biogas production, carbon sequestration, contaminant remediation and nutrient recovery in WAS treatment.

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